

Dissociation kinetics of acyclic and macrocyclic polyaminopolycarboxylate complexes of yttrium

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Dissociation kinetics of Y^{III} complexes of a linear as well as two macrocyclic polyaminopolycarboxylates, ethylenediamine diacetic acid (EDDA), 1,7-diaza-4,10,13-trioxacyclopentadecane- N,N' -diacetic acid (K21DA) and 1,10-diaza-4,7,13,16-tetraoxacyclooctadecane- N,N' -diacetic acid (K22DA) have been studied at a constant ionic strength (0.1 M) under varying $[H^+]$ and temperatures. Cu^{II} ion acts as the scavenger of the free ligand. Dissociation rate of Y^{III} -K21DA is insensitive to Cu^{II} and acetate (used as buffer anion) concentrations. Kinetic stability of the three complexes follow the order: Y^{III} -K22DA > Y^{III} -K21DA > Y^{III} -EDDA. Enthalpies of activation for K21DA and K22DA complexes of Y^{III} are also evaluated. Thermodynamic stability constant ($\log K$) for Y^{III} -K22DA complex is 10.81 ± 0.04 .

Monoclonal antibodies may be linked to drugs or radioisotopes as targeting agents in the diagnostic as well as therapeutic applications for several diseases¹. Central to the success of such an approach is the development of bifunctional complexing agents which can be attached to a protein and can bind the given metal ion rapidly and selectively and yet form a complex which is kinetically inert with respect to dissociation either by acid or cation promoted pathways. The choice of complexing agent is determined by the nature of the metal ion to be bound². Due to growing interest in ^{90}Y (a pure β emitter, β_{max} : 2.25 MeV, $T_{1/2}$: 64 h and a stable decay product: ^{90}Zr) based radiopharmaceuticals, there is a need to develop kinetically inert complexes of Y^{III} to overcome the associated toxicity problems such as the bone localising tendency of the metal ion. The premature release of ^{90}Y leads to the depletion of the immune cell population due to irradiation of proximate bone marrow. Therefore, the ligand chosen to bind ^{90}Y must form a complex which is resistant to *in vivo* yttrium dissociation. The ligand should form a neutral or cationic complex with the metal ion of interest in order to minimize any interaction with protons or cations.

In recent years, a number of C-functionalized derivatives of acyclic polyaminopolycarboxylates like ethylenediamine tetraacetic acid (EDTA) and diethylenetriamine pentaacetic acid (DTPA) have been developed for complexation of metal ions for *in vivo* applications³. The stability and the dissociation rates of these complexes are mainly influenced by the factors like size of the metal ion, charge density and stereochemical requirements of the metal ion as well as of the ligands⁴⁻⁶. The anionic complexes of yttrium with EDTA or DTPA are either rapidly protonated or attract other competing metal ions present in

human serum (e.g. Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} and Zn^{2+}) to form mixed complexes of reduced kinetic stability.

K21DA

K22DA

EDDA

On the other hand, the macrocyclic polyaminopolycarboxylates are considered to be selective in view of their features like internal cavity size and suitable conformation to allow simultaneous coordination of donor atoms to metal ion⁷. Pre-organisation of the ligand, i.e. the conformation of the ligand in the free as well as in the complexed form, should be very similar to avoid an unfavourable contribution to both the enthalpy and entropy of complexation⁸. It

is desirable to study the dissociation kinetics of the complexes of Y^{III} with such ligands under varying experimental conditions like temperature, ionic strength and pH. The dissociation rate together with the stability constant allows the calculation of formation rate constant which may otherwise be difficult to obtain experimentally by a conventional stopped flow apparatus. Chang *et al.*⁹⁻¹⁴ demonstrated that stability and dissociation rates of lanthanide complexes of these macrocyclic polyaminopolycarboxylates depend on the compatibility of the ionic diameter of the metal ion and cavity size of the ligand, apart from the other factors like conformation of the ligand and charge density of the metal ion.

We report here the kinetics and mechanism of dissociation of Y^{III} complexes with three ligands, viz. 1,7-diaza-4,10,13-trioxacyclopentadecane-*N,N'*-diacetic acid (K21DA), 1,10-diaza-4,7,13,16-tetraoxacyclooctadecane-*N,N'*-diacetic acid (K22DA) and ethylenediamine diacetic acid (EDDA) employing stopped flow spectrophotometry.

Results and Discussion

Thermodynamic stability of Y^{III} complexes : The observed value of $\log K$ (10.81 ± 0.04) for Y^{III} -K22DA complex is similar to that for Y^{III} -K21DA complex (10.85 ± 0.02) reported earlier¹². Ionic radius of Y^{III} for coordination number 9 prevalent in aqueous solution is 1.18 \AA ¹³. Assuming that the cavity radii of crown ethers do not change on substitution of O by N atoms, K22DA offers cavity of 1.45 ± 0.15 and K21DA of $0.98 \pm 0.12 \text{ \AA}$ ¹⁴. Accordingly, Y^{III} is expected to be encapsulated by K22DA but not by K21DA in their respective complexes as suggested by models in our earlier work¹⁵. It has also been demonstrated earlier that whereas Ln^{III} -K22DA complex is associated with one water molecule, Ln^{III} -K21DA complex is associated with two water molecules¹⁶. In spite of these stereochemical differences, similar overall stabilities of the Y^{III} complex species can be explained on the basis of significant configurational entropy loss caused by the interaction of carboxylate groups of K22DA (*trans*-configuration) as compared to that for K21DA (*cis*-configuration)¹⁵. K22DA though accommodates the Y^{III} ion in its cavity, configurational entropy loss caused by the interaction of carboxylate groups is significant and thus release of water molecules does not contribute towards the entropy stabilization as much as it does in the case of K21DA. In view of the lack of encapsulation by K21DA, metal-ligand interaction is weaker and thereby the configurational entropy loss is lower as compared to that for K22DA.

Dissociation kinetics of Y^{III} -K21DA complex :

Independence of k_{obs} on $[Cu^{2+}]$ and $[Acetate]$: In view

of the significantly larger $\log K$ (Table 1) values of the Cu^{II} complexes of K21DA, K22DA and EDDA over the corresponding Y^{III} values, the latter complexes are likely to be

Table 1. Stability constants for Cu^{II} and Y^{III} ions

Ligand	$\log K$	
	Cu^{IIa}	Y^{III}
K21DA	16.02	10.85 ^a
K22DA	14.49	10.83 ^b
EDDA	16.20	7.78 ^c

^aRef. 12, C A Chang and M. E. Rowland, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1983, 22, 3866

^bPresent data ^cRef. 18

converted to the corresponding Cu^{II} complexes (if the activation energy required for the dissociation of Y^{III} complex is provided) by the following exchange reaction,

Table 2 shows that the rate constant of the dissociation reaction (1) is independent of the Cu^{II} concentration (range : $0.5 \times 10^{-3} - 2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) suggesting that the rate constant is determined by the dissociation of YL^+ complex as

It is apparent that the formation of Cu^{II} -K21DA complex proceeds much faster than the dissociation of Y^{III} -K21DA complex. It has been proposed that the rate-determining

Table 2. Effect of $[Cu^{2+}]$ on dissociation rate of Y^{III} -K21DA complex
 $[Y^{III}\text{-K21DA}] = 10^{-4} M$, pH = 4.0, $[Acetate] = 5 \times 10^{-3} M$, $\mu = 0.1 M$,
 Temp = $25.0 \pm 0.2^\circ$

$[Cu^{2+}] \times 10^3, M$	$k_{obs} \times 10^2, s^{-1}$
0.5	3.62 ± 0.06
1.0	3.62 ± 0.14
1.5	3.65 ± 0.11
2.0	3.66 ± 0.08

step during the dissociation of $Ln\text{-K21DA}^+$ complex is the formation of an intermediate where the metal ion is outside the ligand cavity but is bonded to at least one of the acetate moieties⁹. The formation of the copper complex is then accompanied by the fast attack of proton and/or copper at the uncoordinated ligand nitrogen(s) which explains the lack of Cu^{II} catalysis. Such an independence of $[Cu^{II}]$ in the dissociation kinetics of lanthanide-CyDTA (cyclohexylene diamine-*N,N,N',N'*-tetraacetic acid) and lanthanide-MEDTA (*N*-methylethylenediamine-*N,N',N'*-triacetic acid) has been reported in the literature^{5,6}. It appears that the copper ion is unable to attack ligand nitrogen(s) to form a binuclear intermediate due to steric constraints imposed by macrocyclic polydentate ligands as long as a bond between lanthanide ion and nitrogen exists.

Table 3 also shows that the dissociation rate of Y^{III} -K21DA complex is independent of the acetate concentration (range : $1.25 \times 10^{-2} - 3.75 \times 10^{-2} M$) at pH 4.75. This indicates that acetate ion is not in a position to replace the

Table 3. Effect of acetate ion concentration on the dissociation rate of Y^{III} -K21DA complex

$[Y^{III}\text{-K21DA}] = 10^{-4} M$, pH = 4.75, $[Cu^{2+}] = 1 \times 10^{-3} M$, $\mu = 0.1 M$,
Temp. = $25.0 \pm 0.2^\circ$

[Acetate] $\times 10^2, M$	$k_{obs} \times 10^2, s^{-1}$
1.25	1.97 ± 0.11
2.00	2.00 ± 0.04
3.75	2.05 ± 0.08

strongly coordinated water molecules present in the complex. This behaviour is analogous to that of heavy lanthanides and is in contrast to the behavior of light lanthanides where acetate catalysis was unambiguously observed⁹.

Effect of acidity on dissociation kinetics of Y^{III} -K21DA :

The observed rate constants (k_{obs}) for reaction (1), the temperature at which these are measured and the concentration of hydrogen ion are summarized in Table 4 for

Table 4. Dependence of dissociation kinetics of Y^{III} -K21DA on $[H^+]$ and temperature

$[Y^{III}\text{-K21DA}] = 10^{-4} M$, [Acetate] = $5 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[Cu^{2+}] = 1 \times 10^{-3} M$,
 $\mu = 0.1 M$, Temp. = $25.0 \pm 0.2^\circ$

Temp $^\circ C$	$k_{obs} \times 10^2, s^{-1}$				
	$10^5 [H^+], M$				
	0.112	0.398	3.8	38	125
15	1.30	1.58	2.54	3.76	4.62
25	1.44	1.61	3.04	4.05	4.98
35	1.49	1.79	3.39	4.38	6.60
45	1.68	1.88	3.83	4.50	6.87

$YK21DA^+$ complex. Fig. 1 shows the saturation curve of k_{obs} vs $[H^+]$ with limiting rate constants at high acid concentration ($3.8 \times 10^{-4} - 1.25 \times 10^{-3} M$). Intercept obtained correspond to the acid-independent or self-dissociation rate constant (k_d). The proposed mechanism is shown in Scheme 1.

Fig. 1. Variation of observed rate constants of Y^{III} -K21DA complex with $[H^+]$ at 25° , $\mu = 0.1 M$.

Scheme 1

Formation of the activated complex species $[YL^+]^*$ and $[YHL^{2+}]^*$ are the rate-determining steps. The rate law assumes the form,

$$k_{obs} = k_d + \frac{K' k_{lim} [H^+]}{1 + K' [H^+]} \quad (3)$$

where k_{lim} is the limiting rate constant for the protonated complex YLH^{2+} and K' the equilibrium constant for the reaction,

Table 5 summarises the k_d , k_{lim} and K' data for Y^{III} -K21DA complex system. These values compare reasonably well with the corresponding data for Lu^{III} ⁹. The k_d values and

Table 5. Resolved rate constants for dissociation of Y^{III} -K21DA complex at different temperatures

Temp. $^\circ C$	$k_d \times 10^2$ s^{-1}	$K' \times 10^{-4}$ M^{-1}	$k_{lim} \times 10^2$ s^{-1}
15	1.35	0.53	3.76
25	1.43	1.01	3.83
35	1.51	1.41	5.37
45	1.55	1.83	5.55

characteristic water exchange/complexation rate constants for yttrium complexes indicate that self-dissociation of the complex does not occur in a single step. It involves the distortion of the complex in the rate-determining step to form an intermediate which by fast attack of hydrogen ion or copper ion gives the product. The reaction sequence may be written as

The water exchange rate constant for yttrium is $1.4 \times 10^7 (M^{-1} s^{-1})$ ¹⁷. When the maximum rate constant for the formation of YL^+ from $(YL^+)^*$ is allowed to be $1.4 \times 10^7 s^{-1}$, the equilibrium constant for the reaction (6) can be calculated as $1.02 \times 10^{-9} (1.43 \times 10^{-2}/1.4 \times 10^7)$. The experimentally determined equilibrium constant for the reaction,

is $7.08 \times 10^{10} M^{-1} (\log K = 10.85)$ ¹² which implies that the equilibrium constant K'' for the reaction,

should be at least $7.08 \times 10^{10} \times 1.02 \times 10^{-9} = 72.22 M^{-1}$ or the lower limit for $\log K''$ is 1.86. This value is very close to that for monoacetate complex of yttrium. The stability constants ($\log K$) for the mono- and bis(acetate) complexes of yttrium are 1.68 and 3.17, respectively¹⁸. Hence, it is very likely that in the active form of the complex $(YL^+)^*$, the metal ion is bonded to at least one of the acetate moieties.

Dissociation kinetics of Y^{III}-K22DA complex : There is a linear dependence of k_{obs} on $[H^+]$ with intercept value of $\sim -0.24 \times 10^{-2}$, suggesting that there is no direct dissociation of the complex. The generalised rate law can therefore be expressed as

$$k_{obs} = k_H [H^+] \quad (7)$$

The value of acid-dependent rate constant (k_H) has been calculated as $1.20 M^{-1} s^{-1}$ which is lower by a few orders of magnitude as compared to the corresponding values for Y^{III}-K21DA and Y^{III}-EDDA complexes, suggesting that it is relatively kinetically inert. Lower k_{obs} value for Y^{III}-K22DA indicates that dissociation is sterically hindered. It can also be adduced as an evidence for the encapsulation of the metal ion in K22DA cavity vis-a-vis K21DA where Y^{III} ion is postulated as outside the cavity. This behaviour is similar to the dissociation of Y^{III}-DOTA complex (1,4,7,10-tetraazacyclododecanetetraacetic acid) which undergoes acid-catalysed dissociation only at low pH¹⁹. However, Y^{III}-DOTA complex appears to be more kinetically inert compared to Y^{III}-K22DA complex. The steric requirements of tetraaza cavity of DOTA impart an unusual rigidity to its metal chelates resulting in extremely slow rate of dissociation of its Ln^{III} complexes. It appears that dissociation of Y^{III}-K22DA complex proceeds through the rapid formation of a protonated species which undergoes a rearrangement to form an intermediate complex featuring a protonated nitrogen atom. The proton transfer from the carboxylate oxygens to nitrogen atom leads to an electrostatic repulsion which assists removal of the metal ion from the macrocyclic cavity¹¹. The observed rate constants for the dissociation of Y^{III}-K22DA complex at different temperatures (15–45°) are given in Table 6 for two different $[H^+]$ (0.012 and 0.016 M). It is observed that the dissociation rate increases with $[H^+]$ and temperature.

Dissociation kinetics of Y^{III}-EDDA complex : Linear polyaminopolycarboxylates exhibit faster dissociation in comparison to their macrocyclic analogs. Similar to Y^{III}-K21DA complex, Y^{III}-EDDA complex ion undergoes dissociation following two pathways, viz. direct dissociation

(k_d) and acid-catalysed (k_H). The effect of $[H^+]$ on the dissociation of Y^{III}-EDDA at different temperatures is shown in Table 7. The dissociation rate is found to increase linearly with $[H^+]$ as well as with temperature. The resolved rate constants are given in Table 8. Solid state IR studies, X-ray crystallography and solution NMR studies of Ln^{III}-EDTA complexes suggest that the protonation site in linear polyaminopolycarboxylate complexes is carboxylate oxygen^{5,20}. The bond between the central metal ion and the coordinating group weakens and leads to the dissociation of the complex.

Table 6. Observed rate constants for the dissociation of Y^{III}-K22DA complex at different $[H^+]$ and temperatures

$[Cu^{2+}] = 1 \times 10^{-3} M, \mu = 0.1 M$

Temp. °C	$k_{obs} \times 10^2, s^{-1}$	
	$[H^+] \times 10^3, M$	
	(12)	(16)
15	1.14	1.63
25	1.38	2.02
35	1.77	2.12
45	1.94	2.23

Table 7. Dependence of k_{obs} on $[H^+]$ for Y^{III}-EDDA complex

$[Acetate] = 5 \times 10^{-3} M, [Cu^{2+}] = 1 \times 10^{-3} M, \mu = 0.1 M$

Temp. °C	k_{obs}, s^{-1}		
	$[H^+] \times 10^3, M$		
	(0.095)	(0.37)	(1.09)
15	0.32	0.37	0.53
20	0.36	0.42	0.64
25	0.39	0.46	0.73
30	0.43	0.61	0.93

Table 8. Resolved rate constants for dissociation of Y^{III}-EDDA complex at different temperatures

Temp. °C	k_d s^{-1}	$k_H \times 10^{-4}$ $M^{-1} s^{-1}$
15	0.30	2.1
20	0.32	2.9
25	0.35	3.5
30	0.40	4.8

Activation parameters : The enthalpies of activation were evaluated for the acid-dependent as well as the acid-independent pathways from the temperature-dependence of the rate constants. Y^{III}-K21DA complex dissociates via two pathways : direct ($k_d = 1.43 \times 10^{-2} s^{-1}$) and acid-dependent showing saturation behavior ($k_{lim} = 3.83 \times 10^{-2} s^{-1}$) at 25° with corresponding enthalpies of activation as 3.6 ± 0.3 and $11.4 \pm 3.4 kJ mol^{-1}$, respectively. On the other hand, the Y^{III}-K22DA complex is less labile as there is only acid-

assisted dissociation ($k_H = 1.20 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$) with enthalpy of activation as $14.1 \pm 1.5 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. The values of enthalpies of activation are of the same orders as reported for heavy lanthanides⁹. The low enthalpy of activation for self-dissociation of $\text{Y}^{\text{III}}\text{-K21DA}$ complex ion suggests a mechanism in which the rate-determining step is the slow distortion of the complex ion leading to an active intermediate. Similarly, the higher value of enthalpy of activation of $\text{Y}^{\text{III}}\text{-K22DA}$ compared to $\text{Y}^{\text{III}}\text{-K21DA}$ complex ion suggests that the former is kinetically inert compared to the latter.

Conclusions : The dissociation of Y^{III} complex of K22DA follows different mechanism as compared to those of K21DA and EDDA. $\text{Y}^{\text{III}}\text{-K21DA}$ undergoes direct as well as acid-assisted dissociation showing a saturation behavior. On the other hand, only acid-catalysed dissociation is observed for $\text{Y}^{\text{III}}\text{-K22DA}$ complex suggesting the latter to be relatively more kinetically inert. The dissociation rate of $\text{Y}^{\text{III}}\text{-EDDA}$ complex is larger by several orders than their corresponding values with ionisable macrocyclic ligands. The rate constants are insensitive to Cu^{II} and acetate concentration for $\text{Y}^{\text{III}}\text{-K21DA}$. Thermodynamic stability ($\log K$) of the two macrocyclic complexes $\text{Y}^{\text{III}}\text{-K21DA}$ (10.85 ± 0.02) and $\text{Y}^{\text{III}}\text{-K22DA}$ (10.81 ± 0.04) are similar in spite of large differences in the kinetic stability. The enthalpies of activation for direct dissociation as well as acid-assisted dissociation showing limiting behavior of $\text{Y}^{\text{III}}\text{-K21DA}$ complex are 3.6 ± 0.3 and $11.4 \pm 3.4 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, respectively. The enthalpy of activation of $\text{Y}^{\text{III}}\text{-K22DA}$ complex for acid-assisted dissociation is $14 \pm 1.5 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. Kinetic stability of the three complexes follow the order : $\text{Y}^{\text{III}}\text{-K22DA} > \text{Y}^{\text{III}}\text{-K21DA} > \text{Y}^{\text{III}}\text{-EDDA}$.

Experimental

Analytical grade EDDA (Aldrich), lithium perchlorate (Fluka), yttrium chloride (Indian Rare Earths Limited), cupric nitrate (SD Fine Chem.), lithium hydroxide (Aldrich) and acetic acid (Merck) were used as such. K21DA and K22DA were synthesised by the reported method with minor modifications²¹ : K21DA $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_2\text{O}_7 \cdot 2\text{HCl}$ [Found (calcd.) : C, 40.97 (41.28); H, 6.78 (6.93); N, 6.80 (6.88)%], decomp. temp. 235°; K22DA $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{30}\text{N}_2\text{O}_8 \cdot 2\text{HCl} \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ [Found (calcd.) : C, 38.13 (38.02); H, 7.60 (7.52); N, 5.93 (5.54)%], m.p. 121.4°.

Dissociation kinetics of the complexes was studied using a stopped-flow rapid kinetic accessory (model SFA-12 from Hi-Tech Scientific, England) connected with Beckman DU-7 spectrophotometer. Temperature was controlled using Polyscience 900 controller. pH was measured using EMCO EE 330A pH meter.

Preparation of solutions : The complexes of Y^{III} with

K21DA and K22DA were prepared by mixing aqueous solutions of metal ion and ligand at pH ~7, whereas for the EDDA complex the pH was adjusted to ~8 using LiOH solution of suitable concentration. The strength of Y^{III} solution was evaluated by EDTA complexometric titration using xylenol orange as indicator. The ligand volume was taken in slight excess (~10%) to ensure the quantitative complexation of metal ion. The complex concentration was maintained as $5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$ for all the reaction mixtures. All the buffer solutions were prepared with a constant acetate ion concentration but varying acetic acid concentration. During these studies, acetate ion concentration in the reaction mixtures was $5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ unless stated otherwise. The $[\text{H}^+]$ was calculated using the expression²², $-\log [\text{H}^+] \text{ pH} - 0.11$. Kinetic studies for hydrogen ion as well as acetate-dependence were carried out at 0.1 M ionic strength (μ) adjusted by LiClO_4 solution.

Potentiometric titrations : All titrations were carried out at constant ionic strength of 0.1 M $(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{NCl}$. The sample solution was prepared by pipetting exact amounts of yttrium and K22DA solutions in the titration vessel from their stock solutions ($1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$) so that the final mixture concentration was $1.2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ both in the metal and the ligand. The titration was carried out at constant temperature ($25.0 \pm 0.1^\circ$). Prior to each titration, the pH meter was calibrated using standard solutions of pH 4.00 (potassium hydrogen phthalate) and 6.86 ± 0.02 (phosphate buffer). $(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{NOH}$ solution was used for titration. All titrations were carried out 4-5 times and reproducible results were obtained. All equilibrium calculations were performed by employing a computer program described elsewhere²³. Data points from 20–80% metal complexation region were employed for the calculation of stability constant.

Kinetic runs : As there was no significant difference in the UV spectral behaviour of the ligand on complexation, dissociation of the complex was monitored by the appearance of an absorption peak corresponding to Cu^{II} complex at 270 nm (for macrocyclic ligands) and 260 nm (for EDDA). Cu^{II} ion concentration used in the reaction mixture was taken in large excess ($\sim 1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$) compared to the complex concentration in order to make the reaction pseudo-first order.

The two solutions in the drive syringes of the stopped flow accessory, viz. (a) the complex solution ($1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$) and (b) the reaction mixture comprising of buffer, LiClO_4 and Cu^{2+} solution were pre-equilibrated at the desired temperature. The kinetic runs were then carried out under varying experimental conditions of temperature and hydrogen ion concentration. The effect of concentration of copper ion (range : 0.5×10^{-3} to $2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$) as well as of

acetate ion (range : 1.25×10^{-3} to 3.75×10^{-3} M) on the dissociation rate of Y^{III} -K2IDA was also studied. Generally reactions were followed upto 4–5 half-lives. Rate constants reported here represent the average value of at least five kinetic runs and are reproducible within $\pm 5\%$.

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